

The Alternative Measures To The Sanctions In The Juveniles' Crimes A Comparative, Analytical Study

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Abstract

If the authentic function of sanctions is an ethical function and its core lies in the deterrence, the basic function of the alternative measures for these sanctions is a utilitarian function that lies in the defense of society to prevent committing new crimes. Based on this, this study investigates the Alternative Measures for the sanctions, which aim to reform and discipline. So if the juvenile deviates, it is not plausible to treat him like the adult criminal for several considerations, including lack of perception and bearing pains of punishment. On the other hand, penal sanctions may corrupt the juvenile in an early stage of his age. Furthermore, his reform without practicing punishment is considered easy in most cases. Therefore, the legislator's goal of practicing alternative measures is rescuing him from the bad situation, refining and treating him when necessary.

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Introduction

Since the alternatives to the sanctions that is determined for the juvenile are the most important among these measures, these are procedures determined by law to face the juveniles' deviation and those who found in circumstances that cause their deviation through following special regulations. For the juvenile judge to be able to choose the suitable measures for the personality of the juvenile, the circumstances of the case and the social circumstances of the juvenile, a number of educational and rehabilitative circumstances stipulated by law must be available in order to select the most suitable one according to the juvenile's situation, (Al-salamat,1997,132). This is due to the difference among the degree of maturity and perception of the juvenile as well as the difference in terms of circumstances of committing crimes from one person to another. An authority must be established in the juveniles' court to select the suitable measures from the list of measures in order to achieve the goals of the legislator. These goals include reforming the juvenile delinquent in sexual crimes, treating him and making him a good member in society, (Abdulatif,2009:213). Jordan has regulated the penal rules of the child in accordance with Jordan law No. 32 of 2014 concerning juveniles. Regarding Morocco, there is no special law concerning juveniles in its legislative pyramid. The penal rules are regulated by the Moroccan criminal procedure code no.22.1 in the articles 458, 517. In the structure of jurisdictional order of the child in Jordan, there is a special juvenile criminal court on the contrary with Morocco, where there is no juvenile criminal court in its jurisdictional structure. Therefore, juvenile judges and counsellors entrusted with juveniles are mandated in a special administrative procedures. Jordan law concerning juveniles divide them into three categories. These categories are the boy under the age of 12, the teen between the age of 12 and fifteen and the teenagers between ages 15 and 18. All of the above-mentioned juveniles may be sentenced with custodial sanctions except for the boy who has no penalty on him. The Moroccan legislator has determined the age of 18 complete years as the age of majority. Juveniles under the age of twelve shall be considered criminally irresponsible due to the absence of the ability to distinguish. Juveniles above the age of twelve and under the age of eighteen shall be considered persons with an incomplete responsibility due to the lack of the ability to distinguish. Article no.8 of the juveniles law permits the placement of juveniles in the foster care or rehabilitating them. Jurisdiction shall be the only authority who can detain them. Accordingly, the juvenile shall be punished according to his age and the crime that he commits.

Regarding the Moroccan criminal code, though the criminal procedure code keeps up with the juveniles' cases and treats them, international agreements and treaties, which the Moroccan kingdom endorsed, suggests that it determined sanctions and penalties on juveniles. The Moroccan legislator permits the detention of juveniles who are above the age of twelve in the prison when necessary or the impossibility of taking other measures.

Problem of the Study

The problem of the study lies in determining the efficiency of the alternative measures for punishing juvenile and its suitability to the practical reality. So some questions are raised:

1. Can forgiveness be lapsed in the law of punishment on the crimes of juveniles?
2. What are the alternative sanctions in the crimes of juveniles, their mechanisms and the terms of benefiting from them?
3. Can the societal sanctions be practiced on the juvenile's crimes and what is its impact on the juvenile reform and reinvolving?
4. Does the criminal legislations for juveniles allow for those who are not members of the jurisdictional and police order to participate in the process of educating and reforming the juvenile and how can this affect the empowerment of the alternatives to sanctions?

Significance of the study

The value of studying the measures for juvenile's lies in considering them a group of procedures that aim to prevent the danger in the child's psychic and protect him and the society in order not to be turned into a real crime in the future. These measures does not aim to forgive sins, causing pains or achieving justice. But rather, it aims to refine and treat the juvenile. Despite the diversity of these measures, all of them agree, in its core, that these are all educational and protective measurements through the discipline and reform of juvenile not on the basis that he is a criminal who deserves punishment, but on the basis that he is a patient who deserves to be treated. Therefore, jurisdiction and Sharia law show in the legislations that determined measures for juvenile's three types of measures in the framework of the utilitarian function according to its purpose. These types include protective measures, disciplinary measures and remedial measures.

Purposes of the study

This study aims to look for all the alternative means for punishing juvenile in order to achieve a high-principled purpose, which is protecting the juvenile from deviation and refine his behavior to re involve him in the society. Accordingly, the study aims to achieve the following goals:

1. Showing the potential to engage parents, custodians, fosters and every trustworthy person in the juvenile reform.
2. Highlighting the role of public interests and institutions and the private institutions and associations that are interested in childhood or entrusted with education, professional training, remedial average or healthy education.
3. Demonstrating the role of the alternative measures for sanctions in treating the deficiencies in the traditional view of criminal justice.
4. Presenting a specialized study about juveniles since they are the nucleus of the society. The stage of juvenility is expected to build their personality and determine the future of their behavior.

Methodology of the study

To determine the alternative measures for sanctions, I followed the descriptive method, analytical method and comparative method in light of both Jordanian and Moroccan legislations. The orientation of the former differs in some cases from the orientation of the latter with the attempt to widen the research to include the dominant regulations and opinions in jurisdiction, legislation and Sharia law. I divided the subject into three topics to investigate the problem of the study. The first topic is related to the measures concerning protecting juveniles. The second topic is related to measures concerning the discipline of juveniles. The third topic is related to measures concerning treating juveniles.

Protective measures for juveniles

Through investigating Jordan law for juveniles, protective measures is considered to be one of the lightest measures stipulated for juveniles. They are imposed on juveniles who committed a crime in an early age or may be exposed to the danger of deviation, (UNICEF, 2018.) the article no.33 of Jordan law for juveniles determines the cases in which the juvenile needs protection. The Moroccan legislator followed the same approach. He approached the care of juveniles, refining their behavior and protecting them. One of the most important updates in the Moroccan criminal procedure code is what article no.512 includes. It determines the cases in which children is in difficult situation and they are the most who need care and protection without committing a crime or being of a criminal action, but they are found in circumstances that put their education, health and morals on the edge of deviation. The Moroccan legislator considers that the juvenile who is less than 16 is in a difficult situation if his physical, mental, healthy and ethical well-being is exposed to danger due to his companionship with deviated people or people who are exposed to deviation, well-known in badness of their reputation or people with a history in criminality. He is also considered in danger if he mutinies on his parents, sitter, guardian, custodian, provider, foster or the person or the institution entrusted with taking care of him. Furthermore, he is also deemed in danger if he used to escape from the institution in which he continues his studies, place of residence or not finding a good place to reside. Beijing rules suggested some measures that the courts can use instead of detaining juveniles in reform institutions like ordering to care, orienting, supervision and keeping under surveillance. Jordan and Morocco adopted these legislations noting that these legislations differ in its number. Some of these legislations increased these measures and the others reduced them. Some of these measures include what is determined for the delinquent juvenile and the others include what is determined for those who are exposed to deviation, (Abdul Tawwab 1995,73). The measures of protecting and taking care

of juveniles include the procedure of handover as the first demand and social surveillance as the second demand. These two demands are investigated as follows:

The first demand: handover of juvenile

Handover is one of the measures that is imposed on the juvenile. It aims to discipline, refinement, protection and preventing the juvenile from getting back to committing crimes (Cantwell,2013). It can be defined as subjecting the juvenile to supervision and surveillance by those who has a natural tendency, actual interest or moral orientation to refine the juvenile and take care of him through imposing restrictions that keep him away from any illegal approach, (Husni,1989, 975). Using this measure is preferred as long as there is no necessity to use more restricted measures, which may affect the juvenile through companionship with other delinquent juveniles, (Child Rights International Network,2009). Additionally, this measure might improve cooperation between the court and the recipient of the juvenile after the latter undertakes to take care of him and not preventing him from his relatives, friends and school, (Abdulatif,2009,211). The majority of legislations stipulated this measure and determined the recipient to whom the deviated juvenile have to be handed over, check out the juvenile during the time of practicing this measure and the responsibility of the recipient in the case of negligence and underperformance in caring for the juvenile during the time of this practice. The measure of handover shall be done by the court like other measures.

Through revising the juveniles' legislations, we notice that it is different in terms of the recipient of the juvenile. The Jordanian legislation followed a special approach in determining the measure of handover. The measure of handover is not determined except for the juvenile himself regardless of the danger of the crime that he commits. Paragraph b of the article no.24 of Jordan law concerning juveniles organized handover of juvenile as follows:

1. The juvenile shall be handed over to one of his parents or those who has custodianship or guardianship on him.
2. If one of the juvenile's parents or those who has custodianship or guardianship on him does not have the competency to educate him, he shall be handed over to the competent of his relatives. If there is no competent among his relatives, he shall be handed over to an entrusted person who undertakes his education or to a trustworthy household to undertake his education after taking the consent of its breadwinner.

The Moroccan legislation followed the same approach. The former allowed juvenile handover to a trustworthy person or an authorized institution or association that can educate him in case of the absence of competent people among the juvenile's relatives.

Handover is deemed a reformative measure through subjecting the juvenile to the supervision of a person who have a natural tendency or an interest in the discipline of the juvenile. This aims to remain the deviated juvenile in the surrounding of his family, in a social care and a homelike environment that is a trustworthy from an educational viewpoint (Stern,1999). Since the measure of handover is one of the protective or preventative measures, it is determined for those who commit a crime regardless of its nature whether it is a felony, misdemeanor or offense at the stage of juvenility, (Al-jukhdar,1998,95-96). When the juveniles' judge select this measure, he calls for the recipient of the delinquent juvenile and raises his awareness on the size of his responsibility and urges him to orient the juvenile in order to avoid getting back to deviation (Unicef,2018).

In order for this measure to achieve its purpose, both Jordanian and Moroccan legislators imposed some restrictions on the judge including taking into consideration, in the case of handover, the obligatory handover explained in the procedure codes provided that recipients must have the ethical guarantees and educate him according to the court's recommendations and the observer of the juvenile's behavior.

Regarding the period of handover, the Jordanian legislator did not determine the period of handover but left it to the evaluative authority of the court as long as the handover is for the parents or the guardian of the juvenile. If the handover is for those who are not relatives of the boy, the period of handover shall not violate one year. The Moroccan legislator did not determine a certain period of handover but made the handover period is reaching the highest age of juvenility, (Abfulatif,2009,220). The period of handover shall not violate this age, i.e the measure of handover shall lapse when the juvenile completes 18 years, (Moroccan criminal procedure code, article no.481, the last paragraph).

Regarding the expense of the juvenile during the period of handover, some juvenile's legislations investigated this matter of the juvenile's expense that the court determines while some of them left it to the general regulations that other legislations determined like both Jordanian and Moroccan criminal legislations. It is worthy to note that Jordan law concerning juveniles does not include an article about the juvenile's expense during the period of handover. However, the paragraph b of the article no. 39 of the same law stipulates that if it turns out that the person who is responsible for the expense of maintaining the juvenile who needs care and protection has the ability to offer the expense of his maintenance totally or partially, the minister or the person who is authorized in writing by him and in behalf of the juvenile who needs care and protection shall take what is necessary to do the jurisdictional procedures of the specific departments to obligate the responsible for the expense according to what is determined by these departments. Regarding the responsibility of the recipient,

some special legislations that took the measure of handover determined the responsibility of the recipient in the case of negligence or underperformance. It is assumed that the recipient undertakes to maintain his behavior and education (Scharf,2005). Some legislations determined a capital penalty in the case of negligence or underperformance while some of them did not consider them in their texts like both Jordanian and Moroccan legislations, (Abdulsatar,1998,115).

The second demand: social monitoring

Social monitoring is defined as a jurisdictional system that tracks the accused or convicted people, monitor them and practice all the available artistic means to know the factors that led to their deviation and assist them to face their personal and social requirements for the sake of treating and refining them outside the penal institutions through organizing their affairs while they remain with their households. it is a method of social research or social service for the accused and convicted people, (Al-asra,1995, 270 and Awad,1995, 129). Social monitoring system is considered a type of penal individualization. Penalty and means of reform fit with the greatness of the crime and the danger of the criminal and his different circumstances, (Rustum,2007, 2). The majority of legislations concerning juveniles adopted the social monitoring system with a difference in the name. Some legislations call it social supervision like the Jordanian legislation. Others call it the guarded freedom like Moroccan legislation. The Jordanian legislator adopted the system of social monitoring as one of the measures that can be practiced on the juvenile. It is defined as putting the juvenile in his natural environment under the supervision taking into consideration the duties determined by the court. The period of jurisdictional supervision may not exceed one year, (Jordan law concerning juveniles, no.24). The Moroccan legislator followed the same approach in this affair. But he called it the guarded freedom. In every court of appeal, the legislator assigns the supervision and the educational tracking for juveniles whom the system of guarded freedom is carried out on them to a permanent or volunteer representative or representatives, (Moroccan Criminal Procedure Code, article no.496). The period of this measure shall extend either during the time of the procedure, reaching the age of 18 years old or insuring his behavior.

In all cases in which the system of guarded freedom is determined, the juvenile or parents, sitter, guardian, custodian, provider, foster or the person or the institution entrusted with taking care of him shall know the nature of this measure, its subject and the commitments that it requires. If an incident reveals an obvious negligence of the juvenile's supervision by one of the people mentioned in the first paragraph of this article or frequent obstacles that prevent him from fulfilling his mission, both the judge or judicial body that ordered to subject the juvenile to the guarded freedom whatever the decision that is taken for him may sentence these people to a civil fine with the amount between 200 and 201 Moroccan derham, (Moroccan criminal procedure code, article no.500). So it turns out that as a measure, social monitoring has the characteristics that make it fulfill its pleasurable goal, which is reform of juvenile and rehabilitating them, through treating them in a natural environment. it also keeps them away from the faults of reform institutions without feeling any change in daily life. Despite the importance of this measure, the practical reality indicates the absence of practice by the juvenile's courts. According to the report of the behavior's observer, this refers to the unavailability of the sufficient staff, who is specialized and fulltime to implement the decision of monitoring effectively. The existence of the observer in the court is nominal. So it is natural not to notice any judicial practices for this measure. This requires increase in the number of the behavior observers, rehabilitating them for this purpose, dedicating them and enrolling in the juvenile's court.

The second discipline: disciplinary measures of juveniles:

The majority of legislations in arab countries determined disciplinary measures. It includes rebuke as the first demand and obligation of certain duties or depriving from some behaviors as the second demand. These legislations enable the juvenile's judge to order one or more of these measures according to the circumstances of the case and the case that he faces, (Al-awji,1986, 74).

The first demand: rebuke

It is a corrective procedure that aims to prevent the juvenile from going into the forbidden or getting back to it. It is considered one of the best measures since it causes a psychological situation in the juvenile through facing him with the illegal action that he committed and warning him from repeating the violation in the future, (Cantwell,2013) since rebuke is enough to deter children, especially who originates in a good environment, (Ja'afar,1996). Several legislations acknowledged this measure but it determined the range of crimes that the judge may sentence to this measure. Rebuke is specified to be carried out only on violations, i.e simple crimes like Jordanian and Moroccan legislations, (Ateya 1999,158). While none of the legislations, which stipulates considering rebuke as one of the measures that can be carried out on the juvenile, determined the phrases or the way through which it can be fulfilled. This means leaving it to the judge. Blaming or rebuke cannot be characterized by violence or force in the phrases that the judge communicates to the juvenile which may affect negatively the psychology of juvenile, (Unicef,2018). Accordingly, blaming or rebuke must be completed in the range of reform and counselling. However, there are some barriers that the judge can not violate. Rebuke shall not be characterized by violence or negative phrases that may leave negative effects in the psychology of the juvenile, which reverse the results of the measure negatively. The judge shall merely blame

the juvenile through explaining the mistake in what he did and recommending him to follow a good approach and warning him from repeating the action. Rebuke shall be communicated by the juvenile judge himself merely by stating orally the sentence itself because it is considered the content of the sentence itself.

The second demand: obligation of certain duties and depriving from doing some actions

Some legislations allowed for the juvenile judge to oblige the juvenile to do some duties as a measure due to a violation in the law. This change includes restricting the juvenile freedom, which may be the cause to commit some actions that are considered a violation of the regulations of the law, (Cantwell,2013). This measure has a corrective nature which aims to support social values and prevent the juvenile from going to places that expose his behaviors to deviation through subjecting him to the supervision of certain people and bodies. Their duty is good orientation of the juvenile, (Abdultawwab,1995, 95). The Jordanian legislator created this measure in Jordan law concerning juveniles 2014. Moroccan legislator did not stipulate this measure though the interest of the juvenile requires adopting it. Additionally, there are some actions that they do and places that they attend contribute as a main factor in their deviation. In the current Moroccan criminal procedure code, the juvenile judge cannot prevent the juvenile from attending a place or working in a profession that were a main cause in their deviation except for in a narrow limitations. So I think that Moroccan legislator should follow the approach of the Jordanian legislator through stipulating this measure explicitly in the Moroccan criminal procedure code.

The third discipline: remedial measures

This type of measures includes enrolling in professional training institutions as the first demand, placement in social institution as the second demand and finally to specialized hospitals and treatment places as the third demand.

The first demand: sending to professional training:

One of the measures that may impose on the juvenile sending to the centers that are specialized in professional training to acquire a career or a profession. There is no necessity for these centers to be governmental. It can be private provided that the judge shall insure following a system that is useful in terms of ethics and rehabilitation, (Al-odwan,2013, 164-165). The majority of juvenile legislations state enrolling in professional training as a continent measure that the juvenile court can sentence. The Jordanian legislator established this measure in Jordan law concerning juveniles 2014. Article no.24 allowed the court adopting any of the noncustodial measures like sending to professional training in one of the specialized centers for a time period that does not exceed one year or sending the juvenile to a rehabilitative programs that the ministry of social development organizes, any civil society institution or any institution that the minister of social development adopts. Jordan law concerning juveniles obliges the head of the house in which the juvenile who needs care or protection resides in allowing for the juvenile to enroll in an educational or training programs provided that he shall come back to the house daily, (Jordan law concerning juveniles, article no.38, A)

In misdemeanors, Moroccan legislator allowed for the judge to issue an order to subject the juvenile to one or more of the measures of the temporary guardianship system through handing him over to an institution equipped for education, studying, vocational training, understate education, public administration qualified for this aim or a private institution acknowledged to fulfill this mission, (Moroccan criminal procedure code, article no.471. the court may order to send the juvenile to a public institution or a private institution for education or vocational training and equipped for this purpose. The criminal legislator aims to the attempt of preparing the juvenile to master a profession in order to make money whether it is mechanical or manual in relation to industry, agriculture or trade. The juvenile court uses this measure if it is proved, after studying the case, that his ignorance, or unemployment, no mastery of a profession or deficiency from making money are the factors of violating the standards that are common among people, (Abdulsatar 1998, 118).

The juvenile judge or those whom he assigns from the court experts visit the training and rehabilitation centers in the range of specialization every three months at least to ensure that it performs its duties in rehabilitating the juvenile to help him in re involving in the society. The social observer undertakes supervises the implementation of these measures.

The second demand: placement in the social reform institutions

This measure is one of the most restricted measures on the juvenile. There are some cases whose treatment is hard inside the family or in the juvenile's natural environment if the latter is unhealthy for the discipline of the juvenile. The deviated juvenile's treatment outside his family and environment is one of the disciplinary fundamental issues in rescuing him from the bad environment that corrupted him or was a main factor in that. Then it led him to the crime. This measure is deemed custodial since it obliges the juvenile to reside in a certain place during its time period and subjects him to a specific daily program, (Altarabolsi,1984, 125).

The majority of juvenile legislations stipulate the placement in the social institutions as a measure that the court may use if it finds suitable to keep the juvenile away from the environment that he lives in. the juvenile may not be detain or placed in the houses of juvenile education, rehabilitating them or caring for them that are stipulated in Jordan law concerning juvenile except in accordance with a resolution from the specialized judicial

department. the judge of implementing the sentence shall visit the houses of sponsoring juveniles stipulated in this law periodically every three months at least provided that he shall deliver a report to the head of judicial council and a version to the minister, (Jordan law concerning juvenile article no.27).

Moroccan legislator stipulated the placement of juveniles in public institutions, not as a custodial measure but for protection and discipline. This can be fulfilled with the ability to sentence the juvenile in detaining in prisons. Moroccan legislator does not stipulate houses of education, caring and rehabilitation like the Jordanian legislator.

The third demand: placement in specialized hospitals

The majority of developed legislations concerning juveniles interested in adopting the placement of juveniles in one of the specialized hospitals as a measure that the judge can use, i.e for the juvenile to receive the required treatment if it turns out that the healthy condition had an effective role in committing the violating behavior. During the time of placement, the juvenile remains under the supervision of the juvenile court during specific times, (Ateya,1999,205). The Moroccan legislator authorized the juvenile judge to place the juvenile in the medical institution qualified for this purpose. This comes when it turns out that the healthy condition of the juvenile requires a medical therapy taking into consideration that his offending may be a result of a pathological or physical tendency, (Al-sharadi 2002, 246). The more it turns out that the action of crime occurs under the effect of a mental disease through which the juvenile lost the ability to perceive or recognize or had a pathological condition that weakened his perception or freedom of choice at the time of crime, the court shall sentence to place him in one of the specialized hospitals. The body undertakes the supervision of the juvenile's case in time periods that may not be exceed a certain limit by law. During this time, doctors' reports shall be exposed to it. It may decide his release if it sees that his healthy and mental condition allows for that. If he reaches the legal age of majority and his healthy condition requires continuing in one of the specialized hospitals for treatment, he shall be transferred to one of the specialized centers for treating the adults, (Hejazi 2007, 156). The breeder often uses means of individualistic psychotherapy and socio therapy. He seeks to cause balance between the groups of juveniles that he handles and to ensure the required educational capacities for them. Special care, group discussions and using theatrics are all means that can be used. The breeder have to show his care and good insight while working under medical and psychological supervision, (Al-malihi,2017, 433). Regarding Jordanian legislation, Jordan law concerning juveniles is free from stipulating this measure. It was worthy for the legislator to mention the measure of therapy as an alternative to punishing the juvenile since the goal of creating a special legislation for juveniles is to understand the real factors of deviation. So if it turns out that his healthy condition requires placing in one of the hospitals before taking hold, then he must be placed in.

Conclusion

After investigating the alternative measures to the juvenile sanctions according to the comparative criminal legislation in both Jordan and Morocco, the researcher concluded a group of results and recommendations as follows:

- Juveniles are often victims of social and familial circumstances that led to take the road of deviation. There is no interest for the society in imposing sanctions on them. But it has an interest in imposing the measures and procedures that protect, rehabilitate and keep them away from the bad circumstances that may lead them to deviation. This is the orientation that the modern criminal policy calls for.
- Though juveniles subject to the relevant social, educational, professional or counselling programs when involving them in juvenile houses, these places still suffer from lack of sufficient human staffing. The fundamental services do not reach the international standards in the area of juvenile justice.
- The ultimate rehabilitative programs do not prove its efficiency notably. Juveniles are exposed to physical and verbal violence inside these houses, whether the cause is the juveniles themselves or the staff who work in these institutions. There is no special programs to prepare juveniles for the stage after detention. They are usually released and handed over to their relatives.
- There is no special system for inspecting the juveniles' houses in Jordan. There are only administrative procedures to visit them and prepare reports about them as well as judicial inspection in accordance with the juvenile's law and the visits of the national center for human rights.
- Both Jordan law concerning juveniles and the procedure code did not acknowledge the idea of transfer. The applicable procedures in both Jordan and Morocco are still merely judicial. Both laws do not allow dealing with the juvenile outside the official procedures or courts.
- The comparative criminal legislation did not include a special integrated system for the alternatives to the detention procedures according to the international criteria. The central section responsible for implementing the non-detention measures that the law stipulates in the behavior observer is the juvenile's parents or custodian. There is no child protection policy that shall be followed by the departments that organize implementing the alternative sanctions. The law contents with the periodic reports that the behavior observer prepares about the juvenile.

- It is noted that Jordan's law does not include the penalty of work for the public interest in the framework of juvenile justice except for limited range. Additionally, there is no special system for girls nor alternative sanctions for them.
- There are several challenges and barriers that prevent from working in an integrated system of sanctions in the range of juvenile justice. the most important of these challenges are as follows:
 - a. the non-acknowledgement of the types of majority of alternative sanctions that are recognized in the international criteria.
 - b. lack of knowledge that the legal community own about a system of alternative sanctions, how it works and putting it in the place of practice.
 - c. no acquaintance of the sociologists and civil society organizations in the system of alternative sanctions.
 - d. having a culture that tends to violence and custodial sanctions in the range of penal justice including juvenile justice.
 - e. weakness of the infrastructure that is required to implement the alternative sanctions and the lack of materialistic capacity and the number of the departments that support the practice of alternative procedures.

Recommendations

1. Generally, the Jordanian legislator did right in terms of giving the juvenile a legislative privacy in a legal age for him. Many legislators did this on the contrary to the Moroccan legislator who stipulated the penal procedures for the child, whether he is a victim or delinquent in the articles of the criminal procedure code which organize the penal procedural aspects for people, whether they are old or young. Therefore, it is recommended for Moroccan legislator to follow the approach of the Jordanian legislator.
2. In every procedural text, Jordanian legislator seeks to achieve the good interest of juveniles in a way that includes all of the stages of his age, especially the child who is exposed to danger and the measures that was legislated to him. This is contrary to the Moroccan legislator who limited the age of the child who needs protection and care in the age of sixteen. In my point of view, this is a legislative barrier toward the benefit of children whose age between sixteen and eighteen from protection and care that they need most. So Moroccan legislator, like the Jordanian legislator, have to widen the concept of a child in a difficult situation to protect the greatest number of children who are exposed to danger.
3. The centers of sponsoring juveniles is one of the most important country institutions in the field of sponsoring offenders and struggling the phenomenon of juvenile delinquency. So the role of these centers must be enabled effectively to minimize the problem of offending through the following suggestions:
 - a. allocating a sufficient budget to meet the pedagogical work for sponsoring juveniles, refining their behavior and supporting institutions within specialized ranges of sponsoring children in order to struggle the phenomenon of juveniles' delinquency. This can be fulfilled through providing all remedial, preventative and structural methods for the sake of rehabilitating and re involving them in the society.
 - b. working in coordination with universities to create majors related to juveniles in order to hire more specialized staff and prepare courses to improve the level of the staff who is responsible for the education of juveniles and the rehabilitation of them.

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